

EMBO Workshop

Comparative genomics of unicellular eukaryotes: Interactions and symbioses

12 – 17 September 2022 | Sant Feliu de Guixols, Spain

About the Workshop

Unicellulars represent ~70% of extant eukaryotic diversity and are responsible for the production of half of all oxygen on Earth. Major challenges in the field are underpinned by this staggering diversity of this domain of life, much of which remains uncultured. Major progress has been achieved in understanding genomes/transcriptomes/proteomes, evolutionary relationships and diversity of selected representatives. Still, for the vast majority of microbial eukaryotes, be they terrestrial or aquatic, we know nothing about their interactions with other living entities. Therefore, with this series of EMBO workshops, which was so far extremely helpful in propelling comparative genomics and diversity of microbial eukaryotes, we will now pay more attention to microbial interactions, as they truly underpin the survival of all life. In order to understand microbial ecosystems, we need to focus on interactions, ranging from ephemeral to permanent, and their evolutionary, physiological, and ecological implications. These topics will be combined with bringing forward the latest developments in the studies of the last eukaryotic common ancestor and non-traditional model organisms and knowledge of their cellular biology – especially as it connects to interactions with the external world. Inspired by the current pandemics, we will also pay attention to viruses affecting this domain of life.

Please ignore any fraudulent company that may contact you for travel and housing arrangement. Housing is included in the registration package and is handled by the organizers.

About EMBO Courses and Workshops

EMBO Courses and Workshops are selected for their excellent scientific quality and timelines, provision of good networking activities for all participants and speaker gender diversity (at least 40% of speakers must be from the underrepresented gender).

Organisers are encouraged to implement measures to make the meeting environmentally more sustainable.

(<http://www.embo.org>)

REGISTRATION DEADLINE

15 August 2022

ABSTRACT SUBMISSION DEADLINE

1 August 2022

CHOSEN PARTICIPANTS WILL BE NOTIFIED BY

11 August 2022

PAYMENT DEADLINE

15 August 2022

Speakers

Lutz Becks

Limnological Institute, University
of Konstanz, DE

Joel Dacks

University of Alberta, Edmonton,
CA

Marek Eliáš

University of Ostrava, CZ

Laura Eme

Université Paris-Saclay, FR

Matthias Fischer

Max Planck Institute, Heidelberg,
DE

Tatiana F. Giraud

CNRS Université Paris-Saclay, FR

Christopher J. Howe

University of Cambridge, GB

Filip Husnik

Institute of Science and
Technology, Okinawa, JP

Nicholas Irwin

University of Oxford, GB

Leu Jun-Yi

Academia Sinica, Taiwan, TW

Anna Karnkowska

University of Warsaw, PL

Patrick Keeling

University of British Columbia,
Vancouver, CA

Mónica Medina

Pennsylvania State University,
Philadelphia, USA

Holly Moeller

University of California, Santa
Barbara, USA

Hélène Morlon

Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris,
FR

Sergio Muñoz-Gómez

Université Paris-Saclay, FR

Eva Nowack

Heidrich Heine University,
Düsseldorf, DE

Giulio Petroni

Università de Pisa, IT

Thomas Richards

University of Oxford, GB

Berend Snel

University of Utrecht, NL

Jeremy Wideman

Arizona State University, Tempe,
USA

Kenneth Wolfe

University College Dublin, IE

Alexandra Worden

GEOMAR, Helmholtz Centre for
Ocean Research, Kiel, DE

Programme

Day 1 | 12 September 2022

10:30 Arrivals, shuttle buses from BCN airport to San Feliu de Guixols

14:00

15:30

17:00

20:00

19:30 Welcome Cocktail

20:00-20:15 Welcome

Julius Lukeš

Keynote/Opening Lectures

20:15-21:15 Molecular and cellular perspectives on a nascent endosymbiosis

Thomas Richards

21:15 DINNER

Day 2 | 13 September 2022

SESSION 1

Chair: **Bacteria, endosymbiosis**

Invited Talk

08:30-09:10 Bacterial and archaeal symbioses with protists

Filip Husnik

Talk

09:10-09:30 Symbioses in stinky mud: Anaerobic protists hosting methanogenic symbionts

Kateřina Poláková

Talk

09:30-09:50 Insights into the hindgut microbial community of
Coptotermes formosanus

Gillian Gile

Talk

09:50-10:10 The role of ciliate protozoa in promoting prokaryotic
species co-existence in the rumen

Ronnie Solomon

Talk

10:10-10:30 Comparative genomics sheds light on the evolution of
association with host cells in Rickettsiales

Michele Castelli

Invited Talk

10:30-11:00 Evolutionary transitions from heterotrophy to
phototrophy: The Mesodinium genus

Holly Moeller

11:00-11:30 COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 2

Chair: Interactions between endosymbionts and their protist hosts

Invited Talk

11:30-12:10 The evolutionary origin of an unusual purple-green
symbiosis

Sergio Muñoz-Gómez

Invited Talk

12:10-12:50 Modeling tools for analyzing the acquisition,
diversification, and macroevolutionary consequences of
host-associated microorganisms

Hélène Morlon

Talk

12:50-13:10 A neo-functionalized transmembrane protein 18 paralog
controls intracellular distribution of bacterial
endosymbionts in a trypanosomatid flagellate
Novymonas esmeraldas

Vyacheslav Yurchenko

Talk

13:10-13:30 Gene gain as a major driver of evolution in chlamydial endosymbionts of protists

Jannah E. Dharamshi

Talk

13:30-14:00 Metabolic interactions between *Monocercomonoides exilis* and its bacterial community

Vladimír Hampl

14:00-15:00 LUNCH

SESSION 3

Chair: Novel features of mitochondria and plastids

Invited Talk

15:30-15:50 Single cell genomics and the diversity of organelle function in alveolates

Patrick J. Keeling

Invited Talk

15:50-16:10 The dinoflagellate chloroplast genome

Christopher J. Howe

Talk

16:10-16:30 Free-living relatives of highly abundant unicellular marine parasites elucidate plastid evolution

Elisabeth Hehenberger

Invited Talk

16:30-16:50 Evolutionary path of secondary plastids

Anna Karnkowska

Talk

16:50-17:10 The net-like heterotrophic amoeba *Leukarachnion salinum* sp. nov. (Ochromyxa, Stramenopiles) has a cryptic plastid

Dovile Barcyte

Talk

17:10-17:30 Evolution of plastids and parasites: capturing the plastid metabolic dependency of the photoparasite, Blastodinium
Victoria Jacko-Reynolds

Talk

17:30-17:50 Comprehensive sub-mitochondrial protein map of Trypanosoma brucei reveals novel metabolic capacities in mitochondrial matrix
Julius Lukeš
COFFEE BREAK

POSTERS - A

18:00-19:30

Flash Talks - A

Chair: 5 x 3 minutes flash-Talks selected from posters

19:30-20:00 TBE

20:00 DINNER

Day 3 | 14 September 2022

SESSION 4

Chair: Protist endosymbioses and diversity of protein complexes

Invited Talk

08:30-09:10 The persistent homology of mitochondrial ATP synthases
Jeremy Wideman

Invited Talk

09:10-09:50 Endosymbiont-targeted host proteins: a key to understand microbial endosymbioses
Eva Nowack

Talk

09:50-10:10 Duplication of a horizontally transferred xyloglucanase: interesting facet to the Red Queen co-evolutionary

dynamic

Vicky Attah

Talk

10:10-10:30 The multipartite syntrophic consortium of *Pelomyxa schiedti*

Sebastian Cristian Treitli

Invited Talk

10:30-11:00 Biodiversity and genomic evolution of bacterial symbionts in *Ciliphora*: an overview through selected examples

Giulio Petroni

11:00-11:30 COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 5

Chair: Interspecies interactions and population genomics of yeast

Invited Talk

11:30-12:10 Multiple convergent events of recombination suppression on fungal mating-type chromosomes : patterns and evolutionary causes

Tatiana F. Giraud

Invited Talk

12:10-12:50 Killer toxins and evolution of the genetic code in yeast nuclear genomes

Kenneth Wolfe

Talk

12:50-13:10 A light sensing system in the common ancestor of the Fungi

Luis Javier Galindo

Talk

13:10-13:30 Finding the genetic contribution to the growth of 1000 yeast isolates in acidic and alkaline environments

Giancarlo Bruni

Talk

13:30-14:00 S. pombe wtf drivers exploit an essential transcriptional network to ensure meiotic drive
Ananya Nidamangala Srinivasa

14:00-15:30 LUNCH

SESSION 6

Chair: Evolutionary and functional genomics of aquatic protists

Invited Talk

15:30-16:10 Moving past lcs and Omes to understanding function and interactions of marine protists
Alexandra Worden

Invited Talk

16:10-16:50 Comparative genomics of coral bleaching
Mónica Medina

Talk

16:50-17:10 Red algae trigger multicellular development in the choanoflagellate *Salpingoeca rosetta*
David Booth

Talk

17:10-17:30 Do genomic traits explain nitrogen and phosphorus requirements in phytoplankton?
Carlos Caceres

Invited Talk

17:30-18:00 The feedback between selection and demography shapes genomic diversity during coevolution
Lutz Becks

18:00-18:30 COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 7

Chair: Features of the Last Eukaryotic Common Ancestor

Invited Talk

18:30-19:10 *Mantamonas* nuclear and mitochondrial genomes reveal ancestral gene content

Laura Eme

Talk

19:10-19:30 The origins of the complex spliceosome in the eukaryotic ancestor

Julian Vosseberg

Talk

19:30-19:50 A new player has entered the game: Anoxychlamydiales and the origin of anaerobic metabolism in eukaryotes

Courtney Stairs

Talk

19:50-20:10 Microbial nibblers form a new supergroup of eukaryotes

Denis Tikhonenkov

Talk

20:10-20:30 Origins of ubiquitin-like modifiers across the tree of life

Mark Field

20:30

DINNER

Day 4 | 15 September 2022

SESSION 8

Chair: Comparative genomics of protist

Invited Talk

08:30-09:10 Jotnarlogs: Ancient cellular machinery lost in animal and fungal model systems

Joel Dacks

Talk

09:10-09:30 Recovery of eukaryotic metagenome assembled genomes from decade-long metagenomic time-series in freshwater lakes

Roudaina Boukheloua

Talk

09:30-09:50 Divergent genomic trajectories predate the origin of animals and fungi

Eduard Ocaña-Pallarès

Talk

09:50-10:10 Chromosome-level assemblies from diverse clades reveal limited structural and gene content variation in the genome of *Candida glabrata*

Marina Marcet-Houben

Talk

10:10-10:30 Breaking bad: Genome evolution of free-living diplomonads

Martin Kolísko

Talk

10:30-11:00 Non-triplet genetic code in *Euplotes* ciliates evolved as a result of neutral evolution

Pavel Baranov

11:00-11:30 COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 9

Chair: Comparative genomics of protists and endosymbiosis

Invited Talk

11:30-12:10 The spread of the first introns in duplications during eukaryogenesis

Berend Snel

Invited Talk

12:10-12:50 Phenotypic characterizations of the endosymbiotic relationship between green algae and two ciliates

Jun-Yi Leu

Talk

12:50-13:10 Diverse genomes and mitochondrial-related organelles in a novel clade of metamonads

Shelby K. Williams

Talk

13:10-13:30 Omics-informed cell biology sheds some light on the molecular secrets of microbial protoplast feeders

Sebastian Hess

13:30-15:00 LUNCH

15:00 **social activity/ad hoc session(s)**

17:00-20:00 COCTAIL MEETING

20:00 DINNER

Day 5 | 16 September 2022

SESSION 10

Chair: Aquatic endosymbioses and more

Talk

08:30-08:50 Uncovering the complexities of Meringosphaera endosymbiosis

Megan Sørensen

Talk

08:50-09:10 Phylogeny, toxicity, and symbioses of benthic dinoflagellates in the Pacific Islands

Yong Heng Phua

Talk

09:10-09:30 Heterogeneous origin and composition of central carbon metabolism in eukaryotes

Carlos Santana-Molina

Talk

09:30-09:50 Endosymbiosis: A prerequisite for the eukaryotic cell biology

Parth K. Raval

Talk

09:50-10:10 Could multiple independent red algal endosymbioses be responsible for the origin of red complex plastids?

Fabian van Beveren

10:10-10:40 COFFEE BREAK

SESSION 11**Chair: Protists and viruses****Invited Talk**

10:40-11:20 Heterotrophic flagellates and their endogenous viruses:
genetic parasites or beneficial symbionts?

Matthias Fischer

Invited Talk

11:20-12:00 Viral-eukaryotic gene transfers reveals insights into
infection mechanisms and the evolution of eukaryotes

Nicolas Irwin

Invited Talk

12:00-12:40 Charting the virosphere of eustigmatophyte algae

Marek Eliáš

Talk

12:40-13:00 Unravelling the molecular bases of algae-virus
interactions in the *Ostreococcus-Prasinovirus* model
system

Sheree Yau

Talk

13:00-13:20 Insight into the genome-wide diversity of prasinoviruses
infecting the alga *Ostreococcus tauri*

Julie Thomy

13:20-15:00 LUNCH

POSTERS B

15:00-18:00

Flash Talks - B

Chair: 5 x 3 minutes flash Talks selected from posters

18:00-18:30 TBE

20:00 DINNER and CONFERENCE CELEBRATION

Day 6 | 17 September 2022

Departures, shuttle buses from San Feliu de Guixols to

BCN airport

DEPARTURES

3:00

6:00

8:00

10:00

14:00

Registration

REGISTRATION DEADLINE

15 August 2022

ABSTRACT SUBMISSION DEADLINE

1 August 2022

CHOSEN PARTICIPANTS WILL BE NOTIFIED BY

11 August 2022

PAYMENT DEADLINE

15 August 2022

- STUDENT/POSTDOCS: EUR 750
- ACADEMIC: EUR 850
- INDUSTRY: EUR 1100

Registration includes:

- Accommodation (shared rooms) at Eden Roc Hotel
- Meals (breakfast, lunch and dinners) at Eden Roc Hotel
- Coffee breaks
- Transfers to/from Barcelona airport

PAYMENT

Accepted participants will receive a payment details by email. Your place will only be confirmed after payment of the registration fee.

By submitting your application to attend this EMBO Workshop, you accept our [data protection guidelines \(https://www.conference-service.com/embo/EMBO_courses_workshops_data_protection.pdf\)](https://www.conference-service.com/embo/EMBO_courses_workshops_data_protection.pdf)

and

[General Terms and Conditions \(https://www.bc.cas.cz//Cds/AdminDownload/?filename=8969_GTC_GoPAY\)](https://www.bc.cas.cz//Cds/AdminDownload/?filename=8969_GTC_GoPAY)

.

SELECTION CRITERIA

The capacity of the workshop is limited to 120 participants. The deadline for registration is August 15th, but we encourage you to register early because the meeting may fill up before the deadline. You will be informed quickly if your registration has been accepted, but your place at the workshop

is not guaranteed until payment of the registration charge is received. The deadline for receipt of payments is August 15th. Applications will be accepted on a first-come-served basis.

All applicants are welcome to submit an abstract and present a poster. Some Abstracts will be selected by the Organizers for oral presentation.

ABSTRACT GUIDELINES

Abstracts must be a maximum of 300 words, excluding title, authors, and affiliations.

POSTER SPECIFICATIONS

The poster space will be 90 x 120 cm (width x height), which corresponds to A0 portrait format.

TRAVEL GRANTS AND REGISTRATION FEE WAIVERS

A limited number of travel grants are available for participants. Applicants do not need to apply separately for travel grants for this event but should indicate on the registration form if they wish to be considered for a travel grant. Selection of awardees is handled directly by the organizer who will notify all eligible participants. More information is available at

[EMBO Travel Grants page \(https://www.embo.org/funding/lecture-travel-and-childcare-grants/travel-grants/\)](https://www.embo.org/funding/lecture-travel-and-childcare-grants/travel-grants/)

CHILD CARE GRANT

EMBO Courses and Workshops offers grants to offset additional child care costs incurred by participants or speakers when participating at any EMBO Courses and Workshop funded meeting. Eligible costs include fees for a caregiver or child-care facility, travel costs for a caregiver, or travel costs for taking the child to the meeting etc. Please indicate on the registration form whether you would like to be considered for the grant. Please also describe how you intend to use the child care grant and specify the sum that you will need.

Contact

Pavla Votrubová

Email: pavla.votrubova@paru.cas.cz

Organizer

Julius Lukeš

Biology Centre CAS, Institute of
Parasitology, CZ

Co-Organizers

Toni Gabaldón

Institute For Research in
Biomedicine, ES

Patrick Keeling

University of British Columbia,
Vancouver, CA

Gwenaël Piganeau

Observatoire Océanologique de
Banyuls, FR

Kenneth Wolfe

University College Dublin, IE

Alexandra Worden

GEOMAR, Helmholtz Centre for
Ocean Research Kiel, DE

Venue

Hotel Eden Roc (<https://www.edenrochotel.com/en>)

[SHOW ON MAP](#)

ACCOMMODATION

The EMBO Workshop will be held at Hotel Eden Roc, in Sant Feliu de Guíxols, Costa Brava, Spain. Sant Feliu de Guíxols is a small picturesque town situated on the northern Mediterranean coast of Spain, 120 km from Barcelona airport. The hotel overlooks the sea and is located 1.5 km from the centre of Sant Feliu de Guíxols.

Most of the rooms in Hotel Eden Roc will be twin rooms shared by 2 people. If you know who you would like to share a room with, please enter their name in the registration form.

TRANSPORT

Travel by plane

Barcelona (El Prat) airport, BCN: The hotel is located 120 km from Barcelona airport, which is served by most major airlines. Shuttle buses to/from Barcelona airport will be provided on the arrival day (Monday 12 September) and departure day (Saturday 17 September)

In addition, **Sarbus** (<https://compras.moventis.es/en-GB>) offers bus service between Barcelona BCN airport and Sant Feliu Guixols.

Travel by train

Girona is the nearest train station (30 km). **Teisa** (<http://www.teisa-bus.com/ca/rutes>) offers bus service between Girona City and Sant Feliu de Guixols. A taxi from the train station to St. Feliu costs around EURO 70.

Travel by car

Motorway A-7, exit 9 (when travelling from Barcelona), or exit 7 (when travelling from France). GPS coordinates for Hotel Eden Roc are: 41.772841, 3.030318.

EMBO
reports

EMBOpress

GORDON AND BETTY
MOORE
FOUNDATION

[Privacy policy](#)

The scientific programme of this event, as submitted at the time of application, was reviewed and approved by the EMBO Course Committee. Responsibility for subsequent changes to the programme, and the organisation and execution of the event, lies exclusively with the event organisers.

EMBO hosts this website but does not take responsibility for the content provided by the organisers of the meeting.